

The Dream of Green Tires

by Jan Malkus

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Foreword	3	Virgin Carbon Black	12
The History of Tires	4	Characteristics of Carbon Black	12
The Beginning: The Wheel	4	Rubber Carbon Black	12
The Invention of Vulcanization	4	Info box: Carbon Black Categories for Automotive Tires	12
The First Tire	4	Manufacturers and Figures	13
Between Solid Rubber and Air	4	Sales Forecast	13
Info box: Vive la Révolution!	4	Carbon Black Production – Then and Now	14
Info box: Inspired by Bicycle Races	4	ELT Management – Modern Utilization of Used Tires	15
Mass Production Begins	5	ELT Management – The Basics	15
From the Tire Industry to a Global Business Sector	5	Facts, Figures and Data	16
Modern Tires	5	What Exactly is Pyrolysis?	16
About the Trees in Tires	6	The Status Quo – What Happens in Conjunction with the Used Tire Pyrolysis?	16
What is Caoutchouc?	6	Results of the ELT Pyrolysis – What Do We Gain?	17
Columbus and the Balls	6	Market and Manufacturers	17
An Expedition into Uncertainty	6	The Revolution – Virgin Recovered Carbon Black?	18
From Clothing to Glue to Hot Air Balloons – Initial Uses	6	The Problem: The Value Chain is Not Closed	18
Info box: The First Chewing Gum?	6	Executive Summary:	18
Generations of Caoutchouc – How, When, Where?	7	The Solution: Sustainable Recycling Methods	19
Rubber Manufacturing Today	7	Revolution: Cleaning Process Deploying Nano Technology	19
Sustainable Production of Caoutchouc	7	The Prerequisites	19
Info box: Synthesis of Caoutchouc as a Factor in Times of War	7	The Process	20
Processing of Caoutchouc	8	The Result: A Closed Value Chain	21
Info box: How is caoutchouc generated?	8	Potenzial Kreislaufwirtschaft: Einfluss auf die Umwelt	21
Interesting Facts Affiliated with Tires	9	Outlook	21
Materials and Additives	9	Conclusions	22
Tire Structure and Components	9	About The Author	24
Tread	9	Literature & useful links	25
Steel belt	10		
Carcass	10		
Production Process	10		
Manufacturers and Statistics	10		

FOREWORD

Just contemplating the title of this elaboration, one thing becomes instantly clear: here is a subject matter that in the broadest sense addresses an environmental issue. For several years I have been researching environmental problems, and investing in technologies that aim to contribute to making society's way of life more sustainable - after all, planet Earth is in a deplorable condition. In my opinion, technologies deployed, questionable ideologies, and improper production cycles all play a primary role when it comes to these issues. Globally, we will have to immediately change our way of thinking in order to develop a sustainable recycling solution for the production of all products which currently have a significant environmental footprint. To that end, nature should be a source of inspiration for us as we work towards technical solutions. After all, nature does not generate any waste. Everything is based on interacting environmental cycles, which humans, unfortunately, have thrown massively out of balance. We continue to do this. Waste is a human invention and it has moved into a direction we must most definitely correct. There is only one solution: All processes, products and product cycles must be aligned in such a manner that all components are recyclable or reusable. The term "Made for Recycling" is establishing itself in the industry. By adopting this concept, manufacturers have the opportunity to demonstrate to their clientele that they place serious emphasis on functional recycling and that they are assuming responsibility for the protection of the climate and the conservation of resources.

Readers who are over 40 will likely remember the early days of paper recycling. Recycled paper looked gray or dark beige and the fiber content was clearly visible. The paper was neither smooth nor white. As the years progressed, recycled paper evolved into an increasingly smooth and brighter product that is hardly distinguishable from newly manufactured paper. The pan-European recycling quota of paper has long exceeded 70 percent and continues to increase. Consequently, the paper industry provides an excellent example of well-functioning recycling, even if there is still inherent optimization potential.

Unfortunately, a large number of major negative examples weigh more heavily on the balance sheet: The global tire market is definitely an example of dysfunctional recycling concepts. With approximately 1.2 billion tires per year, it is a market of gigantic proportions (Wikipedia, 2022). To this day, however, not a single tire on this planet can be fully recycled, which above all results in this enormous negative environmental impact. Tires are "retreaded" until they are finally disposed of. "Tire retreading" is a process of reconditioning worn tires. The base of the tire is

reused, while the tread and sides are completely replaced. In this way, the base of the tire is retained, and material and energy are saved; what remains is disposed of, sometimes reasonably sensibly, but sometimes utterly unspeakably: In some emerging countries, unfortunately, old tires are still incinerated or - as in Kuwait and Qatar - end up in veritable tire graveyards (Rabeder, 2021). In Europe, the United States and Asia, tires now tend to increasingly end up in a pyrolysis system with the intention of professionally recycling them. In this context, one trend is in evidence: at last there are countless enterprises that are working on the subject matter of used tire disposal. They all use a similar system. First, the steel in the tires is isolated, followed by oil and gas. What remains is black mass that largely consists of carbon. It is called Recovered Carbon Black. This is basically Carbon Black, which together with rubber is a key component in the tire manufacturing process. However, after the pyrolysis process, the reclaimed Carbon Black is contaminated with up to 20% ash, which is produced by the additives used in the production of the tire. As a result, without further improvement of its quality, the Recovered Carbon Black from the pyrolysis process is only suitable for the production of new tires to a very limited extent. However, numbers speak for themselves: every passenger car tire contains around 3 kg of Carbon Black, without this substance tires would not even exist. On average, a modern tire contains 25 different components and more than 10 rubber mixtures - depending on the requirements - which makes it almost an industrial marvel (Fraunhofer Institute, 2021). In conjunction with this, Carbon Black plays an especially important role: This industrial black carbon is actually a specifically manufactured elementary carbon in the form of colloidal particles. The environmental impact of the Carbon Black production is immense: The material is largely manufactured by deploying incomplete combustion processes or thermal decomposition of gas-like or liquid hydrocarbons under controlled conditions. The product that is generated is a black, fine, very dusty powder. To produce one ton of new Carbon Black, around 44 GJ (approximately 12.2 MWh) of energy per ton are required, which is equivalent to an emissions rate of about 3.3 tons of CO₂ - an extreme environmental footprint (Fraunhofer Institute, 2021). However, if the industry were now to achieve the feat of once again optimizing the Recovered Carbon Black which remains as a residue when recycling tires, to an extent that would largely eliminate the ash content, thus rendering it equivalent or similar to Virgin Carbon Black, then a true recycling option for the tire industry would be in place and we would eliminate one more gigantic environmental sin. This is the driving force behind my decision to write this paper, addressing more closely the subject matter at hand and providing you with an overview.

THE HISTORY OF TIRES

The history of tires does not only provide insights into exciting factors affiliated with the tire as a product, but also into the technological progress made in human history. This is why it is essential to first and foremost investigate the historic links.

The Beginning: The Wheel

The basis for the invention of the tire was initially provided through the invention of the wheel - and here we have to jump back a few years: The first archaeological finds can be traced back to the middle of the fourth millennium BC during the advanced civilization of the Sumerians in Mesopotamia. These ancient finds were heavy disc wheels made of wood. Another 2,000 years would pass however before the first spoke was introduced to provide some weight reduction. Military purposes were in the foreground of this innovation. By then, the available metal was not only used for the production of weapons or tools, metal fittings also served to improve the composite strength and to optimize the wheels of agile chariots, Thus, wheels became more stable - but for a dampening to be created and introduced, we have to jump historically further forward again (Nagel, 2017).

Info box: Vive la Révolution!

The feudal society of the Middle Ages only began to crumble in conjunction with the early days of the French Revolution in 1789. The political and social liberation process of populations from tribal societies lasted for over a century, but it fostered economic development: the Industrial Revolution spurred new industries that used materials that had not been in demand before and rubber was one of them (Schubert, 2008).

The Invention of Vulcanization

To actually even conceive the idea of turning a wheel into a tire, one material is of course lacking: In the fledgling United States of America of the 18th century, a fertile ground for new ideas, autonomous inventors and highly motivated leisure time tinkerers evolved over an extremely short period of time. This included, for instance, US iron goods dealer and chemist Charles Goodyear, who was looking into the possibility of making water proof clothing. Even then, caoutchouc was the most promising substance he was trying to plastify. Legend has it that while conducting experiments in his household kitchen, Goodyear once dropped a piece of rubber treated with sulfur onto a hot stove. The supposed mishap resulted in a discovery: The resulting fabric became soft, flexible and remained permanently elastic. This discovery was groundbreaking. In 1844 he was granted a patent for the process, now referred to as the

“vulcanization” process. This was the debut of a material we will explore in more detail later (Klein, 2017).

The First Tire

In 1845, the Scotsman Robert William Thomson filed a patent application for a pneumatic tire with a vulcanized tube for carts, but found no takers for his idea, although the tire had been successfully tested in 1847. Veterinarian John Boyd Dunlop, also from Scotland, was working on a similar idea at the same time: the development of a pneumatic bicycle tire, which he successfully patented in 1888. This came just at the right time, because in the meantime the first automobiles had been built - such as the first horseless carriage developed by Gottlieb Daimler (Neumayer, 2018). This allowed rubber to develop rapidly as a material in Europe, as well as the tire: Dunlop's tires, whose rubber tubes with soccer valves were still bandaged onto a rim, quickly developed into a bicycle tire through Charles Welch's drop-center rim, which offered enough space for an insertable, air-filled tube. As a result, the pneumatic tire was invented! (Nagel, 2017)

Info box: Inspired by Bicycle Races

Not long after the first bicycles attained a certain level of riding comfort and rendered them road-worthy, early bicycle races were organized. In 1892, the French professional cyclist Charles Terront won the first edition of the Paris-Brest-Paris cycling race with a lead of over eight hours, his bicycle running on the Michelin brothers' advanced pneumatic tires. Motivated by this success, the brothers quickly transferred this process to the car, which, although it did not win its first race in 1895, made it to the finish line on pneumatic tires - a milestone in the development of the car tire as we know it today. (Nagel, 2017).

Between Solid Rubber and Air

Initially, tires made very little progress around the turn of the century. Solid rubber was still being used in most cases, although the Michelin brothers' experiment had been quite sensational. Thus, bicycle tires remained technologically superior to car tires for quite some time. Above all, the wear and tear was remarkable: The first tread tires launched by the Continental company had a mileage range of just 500 kilometers. This changed only after the further development of rubber compounds: Until then, tires consisted of natural rubber and sulfur with some additives such as zinc oxide, chalk or similar. The addition of Carbon Black was the only option available to make the material more durable, stronger and longer lasting - the mileage of a tire increased by a factor of 10 as a result, tires were now black all over the world (Burt, 2021).

Mass Production Begins

In the early 20th century, motorized vehicles began to conquer the markets. Mass production emerged, the demand was high and more cars and thus tires were needed. However, even back then, the raw materials were soon in short supply: Even before World War I, the production of caoutchouc on plantations exceeded the manufacturing based on wild caoutchouc. The rising price of the commodity led to efforts to produce rubber synthetically. In principle, this was already possible: In 1909, the Bayer company in Germany was granted patents for polyisoprene and methyl rubber - but the artificial substances were not yet ideally suited for tire production.

Further experiments were carried out with various materials to accelerate the process of vulcanization and in turn slow down the aging process of the tires. After the end of World War I in 1918, the pneumatic tire had also arrived for trucks; long distances had to be covered with a full load. Driving comfort was much better with an air-filled tire than on solid rubber. This can be attributed to the fact that a solution - dampening - had finally be developed which had not existed since the previously described antiquity. Aired-up tires compensated for any uneven surfaces much more effectively and thus made it possible to also drive at higher speeds (Nagel, 2017).

From the Tire Industry to a Global Business Sector

On fast rolling lines, tires were further developed. Their structures were now more robust, the profiles had been optimized, the fit on the rims was reinforced, new materials were being used and installed. Hence, tires proved to be sturdier and simultaneously more flexible. This also resulted in the optimization of the tires' useful lives, so there were fewer breakdowns and the number of vehicle operators increased. The caoutchouc synthesis once again accelerated and the demand for raw materials was greater than ever before. Thus, a complete industry emerged with different production cycles, services, forms of trade, development sites and new professional skills. While rubber synthesis rapidly became more advanced during World War II, the car tire also made further advancements in development: Before the end of the war, the Continental company was awarded a patent for a tubeless tire concept - the basis for today's standard car tire. After the end of the war, the Michelin company set the next milestone in tire technology in 1946: the patent for the radial tire with a steel belt, whose carcass threads are arranged at right angles to the direction of travel, revolutionized tire construction. The mileage was doubled once again, and steering precision reached a new level (Continental, 2022).

Modern Tires

The modern car tire now has no tubes but rolls on a radial steel belt. It is made of synthetic and natural rubber and contains numerous new materials such as polyester, Kevlar and the like, which reduce the weight and the rolling resistance. In addition to technology, the market is undergoing extreme changes: Only three tire manufacturers now dominate around 40 percent of the global market. Digitization is making headway into the tire industry. It is also clear that automotive production is trending upward: We are now at just under 1.3 billion passenger cars worldwide (German Federal Environmental Agency 2022) - not counting commercial vehicles - and these vehicles all require four tires plus replacements. This also makes it clear that throughout history, not only progress but also the environmental impact of tire production has increased - and exponentially: CO2 emissions, microplastics and particulate matter from abrasion, and many other factors foster this trend. In conjunction with this, the most significant are, however, the inefficient and unsustainable product cycles that are conclusive up to this point as a result of the historic categorization. To further investigate this subject matter, the following chapters will focus on the examination of the original material – caoutchouc.

ABOUT THE TREES IN TIRES

Below, we will find out more about the material that made the production of the tires we are familiar with today even possible. Merely contemplating its history or evolution is an exciting exercise: From the Amazonian rain forests to its place under the axle of any vehicle we see driving down the street... How did all of this happen?

What is Caoutchouc?

Let's begin by quickly reading the entries on the German Wikipedia site (direct translation from the German 2022 Wikipedia entry, not the English entry): "Natural caoutchouc, formerly known simply as rubber, also known as gum elasticum or resina elastica, is a rubbery substance found in the milky sap (latex) of many different rubber plants. The rubber-bearing latex is usually present as a milky liquid, but it can also be present in semisolid form in the plants. The milky sap tastes similar to sweet cream and is edible." From a purely etymological point of view, we also get the following explanation: "The German word "Kautschuk" is a loanword from French caoutchouc and goes back to an indigenous language of Peru via Spanish caucho, formerly cauchuc. In Tupi or Quechua, the expression caa ochu, formed from the words caa (tree, wood) and ochu (tear, blood), stands for the "weeping, bleeding wood" or "tears of the tree." All of this is interesting, but the question is, how did caoutchouc land on the big global stage?

Columbus and the Balls

Caoutchouc was probably known to the indigenous people of the Americas for centuries, long before Christopher Columbus even thought of sailing from Portugal to India and accidentally discovered the "New World." According to the famous historian Antonio Herrera, during his second voyage of discovery of America, Columbus met native people who used "balls of elastic resin" for a kind of ball game. Whether Christopher Columbus was actually the first European to hold rubber in his hands is not absolutely certain, but it is nevertheless a fun anecdote, which does, however, allow us to deduce how long caoutchouc might actually have been a known commodity (Markham, 1892).

An Expedition into Uncertainty

By the beginning of the 18th century, the Enlightenment was already well underway. The focus was on rational thinking, existing structures were to be overcome in order to push progress forward. The young French adventurer and explorer Charles-Marie de La Condamine must

certainly have been excited when he set off from France to South America as part of an expedition in 1735. He had been admitted to the Academy of Sciences a few years earlier and wanted to participate in clarifying the greatest physical debate: that of the Earth's shape. After the surveying and research work was completed in 1745, he decided to make the return trip by a more dangerous route: He became the first scientifically literate man to navigate the full length of the Amazon River. On this journey, he rediscovered caoutchouc and, among other things, presented the material to the French Academy of Sciences upon his return (Feger, 1973).

Info box: The First Chewing Gum?

According to one tale, the Spanish conquistador Hernán Cortés admired the flashing teeth of the Aztec girls, which he attributed to chewing a certain type of gum. When the first small quantities of rubber arrived in Europe from America, the material was also believed to have special healing effects (Feger, 1973).

From Clothing to Glue to Hot Air Balloons – Initial Uses

Charles Condamine explained to the academic world the possible applications of the material he had been able to determine on his journey. Modern research confirms this fact: According to some studies, South American indigenous peoples succeeded in coating cloth with rubber as early as the 16th century, making it water-repellent. Other sources indicate that at the same time, caoutchouc juice was used in Asia as a glue to capture birds. However, the raw material was unsuitable for further processing in Europe in the era of Enlightenment: During the long transport, the caoutchouc milk became tough and solid and could therefore no longer be used (Feger, 1973).

In the mid-18th century, several solvents were found for caoutchouc, including turpentine, enabling the material to finally be used since it could now be moulded and processed. Various products were made from this new, water-repellent material, such as rubber shoes and hoses. The hot-air balloon of the Frenchman Jacques Charles, which made its maiden flight on December 1, 1783, was also made of silk coated with rubber dissolved in turpentine. The rubber boom, which happened thereafter, took the course described in the previous chapter, when Goodyear vulcanized caoutchouc and it was later used in the manner we are familiar with today (Pfitzner, 2016).

Generations of Caoutchouc – How, When, Where?

The fact that the demand for rubber increased sharply at the beginning of the 19th century has already been earlier in this treatise. However, every resource will eventually be depleted: the raw plant material did not yet grow in the moderate climate latitudes where it was processed. Thus, European for-profit companies set up plantations here as well, which were primarily cultivated by slaves. But the vegetation made the operation labor intensive. It was not until British naturalist Henry Alexander Wickham smuggled caoutchouc seeds from Brazil to Europe in 1876 that an opportunity for more efficient cultivation arose. The seeds were sprouted, transported to Southeast Asia, cultivated there and propagated. In British and Dutch colonies, rainforests were quickly cleared in order to establish caoutchouc plantations (Seelinger, 2021).

Info box: Synthesis of Caoutchouc as a Factor in Times of War

The importance of caoutchouc during the world wars is definitive, especially considering the tire production facts explained earlier. With the start of World War II, the European axis powers were cut off from the caoutchouc supply as the Allied Forces controlled the world's oceans. When Japan conquered large parts of Southeast Asia in 1941/42, Great Britain and the USA also had to look for new sources of rubber. Both sides responded to the caoutchouc shortage with efforts to recycle and synthesize caoutchouc (Seelinger, 2021)

Rubber Manufacturing Today

According to the WWF (2022), the rubber tree (*Hevea brasiliensis*), originally found only in the Amazon basin in South America, is still largely cultivated in Asia today: more than 90 percent of natural caoutchouc is produced in Southeast Asia. Because of the trees' temperature and rainfall needs, the trees ideally thrive in tropical regions. The main growing countries are Thailand, Indonesia, Malaysia and Vietnam. In these countries, 85 percent of production is in the hands of small farmers, most of whom have less than three hectares. The first harvest takes place after five to seven years, and the maximum yield is reached after twelve to 15 years - after which the wood is used for furniture production.

Of course, improper caoutchouc cultivation also harbors negative environmental factors: according to the WWF (2022), "in order to create new areas for cultivation, valuable rainforests have already been cleared in the past - especially in the period from 2012 to 2014, when the price of rubber was very high. Deforestation for cultivation results in the release of large quantities of greenhouse gases and thus has a direct impact on climate change. Habitats for numerous animal and plant species are lost as well."

Sustainable Production of Caoutchouc

In spite of all the environmentally harmful factors, rubber trees basically have a very positive impact on nature: For example, they can bind a great deal of carbon dioxide from the air and thus contribute to climate protection. A basic prerequisite is that no forests or other natural ecosystems are destroyed for the cultivation of rubber. According to the WWF (2022), the sustainable cultivation of natural caoutchouc can be effectively implemented by deploying the proper method - such as through an agroforestry system in which rubber trees are combined with other tree species such as fruit trees and evergreens. Through diversification, pests cannot spread as quickly, trees and plants benefit from each other, and the soil is enriched with nutrients, etc.

"Such systems are more resilient, have the potential of sequestering carbon and use resources such as water, light and nutrients more efficiently. This also reduces the risk of pest infestation when compared to monocultures, which is why the use of pesticides can be cut significantly or dispensed with altogether. By using higher-quality seedlings, the yield of the trees can also be sustainably increased." (WWF, 2022).

To demonstrate what such a plantation might look like, I would like to now share some impressions I gained on an innovative caoutchouc plantation I visited in Ghana.

Info box: How is caoutchouc generated?

The trunks of rubber trees are scratched to produce natural caoutchouc. The escaping plant milk - latex - is collected and then acidified with vinegar acid. As a result, the milk coagulates and can be skimmed off for further transportation and processing

Photos by Jan Malkus

Processing of Caoutchouc

Rubber processing is a complex process, but one that is relevant for what we will look into later. Hence, I'll keep it short, concise and to the point: The starting material for caoutchouc proces-

sing are so-called rubber polymers, which are processed with other components to form a compound. The following basic components are of importance:

1. Polymer(s)
2. Filler material(s)
3. Softeners
4. Minor chemical components
5. Cross-linking chemical components

The first distinction to be made between rubber polymers is that there are natural caoutchouc materials and synthetic rubber materials. Natural caoutchouc is more elastic and highly tear resistant, which is why it is usually used for products that require more extreme mechanical and solid dynamic properties, such as for instance tire tread. Among the many synthetic rubbers, styrene-butadiene rubber is the most common. The copolymer of styrene and butadiene is a cost-effective general-purpose rubber. The use of plasticizers subsequently improves the processing and vulcanization properties of the rubber compound. The final basic building blocks of the compound are then so-called crosslinking and minor chemicals. This group includes processing aids, anti-aging agents and specialty chemicals, etc. Finally, the crosslinking is largely the result of adding sulfur or peroxides. For this process, too, various chemicals are added to the compound. When the rubber compound contains all the necessary components and is of the required quality, the molding process begins. The most important molding processes in the rubber industry are compression molding, injection molding, calendaring and extrusion (Deutsche Kautschuk Gesellschaft e. V., 2018).

Once again, it is clearly evident which historical steps had to be taken, which social and political dimensions played a role and what is technically necessary before a tire can even go into production. And this is only part of the environmental impact. For the sake of completeness, let us gather some facts about tires below to complete the general overview. Thereafter, we will be ready to move on to the real issue at hand: Can tires really be produced in a sustainable recycling economy?

INTERESTING FACTS AFFILIATED WITH TIRES

We have now investigated some of the historic background information, interdependencies and general facts. To gain a better overview, we will once again examine tires – how are they made, what is required and what are their components. Compared to other industrial processes, tire production is in fact a rather conclusive process. However, several steps have to be taken, which, upon an in-depth look, prove to be highly complex. Moreover, the aim will be to once again place the focus on the tire market – facts, figures and data.

Materials and Additives

First and foremost, several commodities need to be combined and processed into composite materials. In conjunction with this, various industries, supply chains and product cycles play a role. On average, a modern passenger car tire contains up to 25 components and 12 different rubber compounds. An industry leader in the tire industry, Continental, a renowned tire manufacturer, specified the following components in this context (2022).

1. Steel

The steel industry supplies high-strength steel, which is the base material for the production of the steel belt (steel cord) as well as the wire cores (steel wire).

2. Chemicals

Tire manufacturing requires numerous chemical components such as synthetic rubber and other materials that improve a tire's resistance to wear, aging, and that optimize traction.

3. Natural caoutchouc

As previously described, the milk-like liquid (latex) extracted from the trees clumps thanks to the addition of acid. This clump is subsequently cleaned with water and pressed into firm balls, which simplifies the material's transportation and storage. The balls are portioned, cut to size, weighed and then mixed with other additives according to a precise recipe. Up to twelve different rubber compounds are used for a modern passenger car tire.

4. Industrial Carbon Black

Industrial Carbon Black is one of the most important fillers deployed in the manufacturing of tires. Carbon Black works like flour in doughs. It binds the caoutchouc and renders it more robust. On their own the different types of caoutchouc would not be able to make a stable compound – industrial Carbon Black is the primary stability contributor and thus improves the tread performance of the tire.

5. Fabric

Special raw materials such as rayon, nylon, polyester and aramid fibers are used in the manufacture of cord to reinforce the base, or foundation, of the tire.

Obviously, it depends on the exact composition, which can of course vary from manufacturer to manufacturer. An example of an approximate volume ratio is provided below on the basis of Continental brand tires:

- Caoutchouc (natural caoutchouc and synthetic rubber) **41 %**
- Fillers (Carbon Black, silica, carbon, chalk, etc.) **30 %**
- Reinforcement materials (steel, polyester, rayon, nylon) **15 %**
- Softeners (oils and resins) **6 %**
- Vulcanization chemicals (sulfur, zinc oxide, etc.) **6 %**
- Materials that prevent aging and other chemical additives **2 %** (Continental, 2022)

Tire Structure and Components

A modern tire consists of various components that build on each other. In total, a modern tire for cars or trucks - as already mentioned earlier - consists of about 25 components. In summary, these can be divided into three categories:

Tread

The tread provides the connection between the tire and the road. The tread pattern and the recipe for the tread compound determine almost all tire properties such as grip, abrasion behavior or rolling resistance.

Steel belt

The steel belt consists of several rubberized steel wires. It gives the tire stability, reduces the wear and tear as well as the rolling resistance to a minimum.

Carcass

The carcass is the skeleton of the tire and thus represents the supporting substructure of every tire. It consists of one or two layers of fabric embedded in rubber. Tensioned by the internal pressure, the carcass gives the tire the appropriate support.

Production Process

In tire construction, all semi-finished products are assembled into a tire blank using a tire building machine: First the carcass, then the tread and belt. In preparation for vulcanization, the blank is sprayed with a special liquid. Finally, the curing process begins: the tire acquires its final shape after being vulcanized for some time under specific pressure and temperature conditions. During this step, the raw rubber is transformed into flexible and elastic rubber - just like in Charles Goodyear's kitchen. The tire also receives its profile and sidewall markings in the molds of the vulcanizing press. (uniroyal.de, other documentation).

This technical overview quickly explains that a high level of effort is involved in the tire manufacturing process - the corresponding environmental impact is not to be overlooked. If you now look at the sales figures of the main players in the tire industry, you get an idea of how strong of a business sector the tire market actually is: Growth is one of the goals - and it happens at the expense of the environment. After all, once a tire has been discarded, it becomes waste, as described at the beginning of this treatise (Statista, 2022).

Manufacturers and Statistics

Revenues of the world's largest tire manufacturers

Allocation of sales in the global tire market based on manufacturers in 2019 and 2020

Used tires based on their use in Germany in 2019

Tire factors that have an adverse impact on the environment

To be able to better assess the specific factors of the production of tires that have an adverse impact on the environment all over the world, I would like to summarize them below:

- Generation of the raw materials required for tire production (iron, crude oil, natural gas, coal, natural caoutchouc)
- Production of the base materials (polymer tissue compounds, steel cord, synthetic rubber, various chemical additives)
- Production of the tires at the plant
- Tire usage
- Disposal of used tires

What stands out is the production of Carbon Black or industrial Carbon Black required for this purpose - an economically significant material. It is produced in combustion processes and consists of almost pure carbon. It has been systematically produced for almost a century - for a wide range of applications and products: So also for the tire. In the next step, we will therefore take a closer look at this industrial Carbon Black...

VIRGIN CARBON BLACK

In the previous chapter, we talked about tires as a product. Now we will immerse ourselves into the material at hand: What exactly is Carbon Black or industrial Carbon Black?

First and foremost, Carbon Black is a black chemical with special applications, available in powder or pellet form. However, this high-tech industrial product has hardly anything to do with flue or diesel soot: The latter is merely a poorly defined by-product that is generated during combustion processes - for example, of coal or hydrocarbons. This substance is also known to be black and is therefore also referred to as "soot" (Fraunhofer IBP, 2022). However, precise information on its structure and composition can hardly be provided, since the changing conditions during formation do not allow uniform products to be formed - especially since the organic and inorganic contamination is relatively high. Since the term carbon is used in German for both types of carbon, the English term "Carbon Black" is now commonly used (also internationally) for industrial Carbon Black. A more precise composition can also be provided: Carbon Black consists of more than 96% finely divided carbon and contains small amounts of oxygen, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulfur (enargus, other documentation).

Characteristics of Carbon Black

Carbon Black is being used by a wide range of industrial sectors: Thanks to the fact that it improves the physical, electrical and optical properties of various materials, it is used primarily to optimize the performance of different substances. The properties of most Carbon Black grades are determined by industry-wide standards - for example, by the German Institute for Standardization (DIN), the International Standardization Organization (ISO) and the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM).

The latter determines in particular the caoutchouc black carbon that are relevant for this treatise. Depending on their field of application, specific requirements change, which can be specifically influenced by the type of manufacturing process and by varying the process parameters (Starwin, 2021).

Carbon Black consists of small, mostly spherical particles, also called primary particles. According to Lumitos AG (2022), these nanoparticles are about 1,000 times smaller than the diameter of a strand of hair. Thus, at these dimensions, it is no longer the chemical composition alone, but

also the size and shape of the particles that determine the properties. These include electrical and magnetic properties, but also hardness, toughness or melting point. As a high-tech material with nano-structuring, Carbon Black thus made it possible, for example, to specifically optimize the three most important parameters of car tires (rolling resistance, wet grip and abrasion).

Info box: Carbon Black Categories for Automotive Tires

There are around 40 different types of Carbon Black for car tires, which give the rubber specific properties. The classification of standard Carbon Blacks according to the US ASTM standard is common internationally. In the CIS countries, the GOST standard is also generally used (Lumitos AG, 2022).

Rubber Carbon Black

As previously described, Carbon Black is used as a component in tire manufacturing for reinforcement, improving resistance, tear strength, conductivity and other physical properties. These so-called "Rubber Carbon Blacks", are the most widely used (and cost-effective) reinforcing material for tire components and technical rubber products, including industrial rubber items, rubber waterproofing membranes for roofs, automotive rubber parts and general use rubber products. Carbon Black also offers protection against ultraviolet radiation due to its high UV resistance: in this respect, it is a kind of "ozone scavenger" and prevents the tire from cracking. It also prevents electrostatic charges, dissipates heat from certain points - especially in the tread and belt areas, which can sometimes reach high temperatures while driving. This reduces thermal damage to the tire, which further extends its service life.

Manufacturers and Figures

Global market shares in Carbon Black production (2018) with a forecast for 2025

The global Carbon Black market is a consolidated market where the top three players - Birla Carbon (approx. 2.1 million tons), Cabot Corporation (approx. 2.2 million tons) & Orion Engineered Carbons (approx. 1.2 million tons) account for about 50% of the market volume.

The largest producers worldwide who hold these market shares include the following companies:

- Birla Carbon
- Cabot Corporation
- Orion Engineered Carbons (ex Evonik)
- Sid Richardson
- BLACKCAT
- PCBL
- Omsk
- TOKAI
- CSRC
- LongXing

- Liaobin
- Mitsubishi
- JINNENG
- Baohua
- Akzonobel
- Lion

(Statista, 2022)

Sales Forecast

In terms of revenue, the global Carbon Black market is expected to grow at a CAGR of 4.4% through 2026. Apart from the tire industry, the main drivers are growing applications in the fiber and textile industries. However, applications for tires and industrial rubber products continue to dominate the market and are expected to grow in the coming years. The Asia-Pacific region leads the global market in this respect, with countries such as China and India - although fluctuations are also apparent here, presumably also in view of the effects of the COVID 19 pandemic. (Statista, 2022).

Example: Production volume of Carbon Black in India in fiscal years 2013 through 2021

Carbon Black Production – Then and Now

The oldest process for Carbon Black production is the "flame soot process", in which mainly tree resins are burned under limited air supply. Although the yield is relatively low at around 5 % in relation to the amount of raw material used, it was the only known process until the 16th century. In the second half of the 19th century, the channel black process was developed in the U.S.A., using natural gas as a raw material for the first time. Today, the process of thermal-oxidative cracking of hydrocarbons - pyrolysis - accounts for the largest share of worldwide production processes, at approx. 98 %. The greatest importance is attributed to the furnace-black process, which is a more economical and flexible process. It is a continuous process running in a closed system: The heart of the process is the so-called reactor chamber, which can be divided into four zones - combustion zone, mixing zone, reaction zone and quench zone. In the combustion zone, the fuel (natural gases) is burned under controlled air supply to form carbon dioxide and water in order to produce the energy required for Carbon Black production. In the mixing zone, the raw material is sprayed into the hot gas stream coming from the combustion chamber. The hot gas mixture finally enters the reaction zone. There, at temperatures between 1400 and 1700 °C, most of the feedstock is pyrolyzed and split into Carbon Black and waste gas. The reaction is terminated in the quench zone, where the hot reactor gas is abruptly cooled to 900 to 1200 °C by the addition of water (enargus, n.d.). The water nozzles are distributed throughout the reactor chamber so that, depending on the flow rate of the reactor gas and desired carbon black properties, the reaction can be stopped at any point. The purified Carbon Black contains large amounts of air or reactor gas ("fluffy Carbon Black") even after separation from the pneumatic system, resulting in a relatively low overall density. It must therefore be further compressed before commercial use. This is done, for example, in stirred tanks or via vacuum compression, in which the Carbon Black is slowly degassed while being stirred (Schmidt, 2003).

Pyrolysis plant with stirring tank

ELT MANAGEMENT – MODERN UTILIZATION OF USED TIRES

Since we discussed the associations of tire in the previous chapters, it is now time to bring this information together in a different thematic focus. We now know how the tire as a product rolled into our lives, what raw materials are needed, and how they are obtained and processed. From an economic point of view, there is no doubt - there is a need, products are created, placed on the market, sold or bought, fulfill their purposes and are discarded at the end of their product cycle. Tires become old tires; new ones are produced. The objectives and the must haves are givens, and they continue to be business and growth driven.

Now let's look at the issue from another perspective - in purely ecological terms, the whole thing looks different: In a fictitious ecological "balance sheet for tires," there would be nothing on the "liabilities" end: Earth's resources - which, by the way, we humans are not (single-handedly) entitled to - are finite and will be depleted at some point. Thus, ethically speaking, there would only be an ecological "assets side," and that would be liabilities to the planet. This has been determined some time ago (even if often only out of economic interest). Recycling is the keyword, the topic of ELT management (End-of-Life-Tire-Management) is now what we have to focus on.

ELT Management – The Basics

Whenever people think about the environmental impact of tires, they usually focus on the management of tires once they are no longer useful (End-of-Life-Tires or ELTs). In this context, there are several options that can be divided into the following three categories:

- Material recycling
- Energy recycling
- Civil engineering use and backfilling

The total amount of ELTs recycled in 2019 as determined by the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) in a total of 13 countries and the European region was approximately 25.7 million tons and 26.1 million tons per year, if we were to take into account civil engineering and backfilling as additional recovery routes. The total amount of ELTs generated in these countries is estimated at 29.1 million tons.

ELT recycling markets worldwide are mainly determined by the regulatory context of each country. Government regulations are enacted to address environmental issues related to the illegal disposal or importation of ELTs, as well as historical stockpiles that create public health and sanitation problems (e.g., fire hazards, breeding grounds for mosquitoes and vermin, and the current problem of the Zika virus, etc.) that may result from ELT collection and processing systems that do not work properly.

Facts, Figures and Data

According to a study conducted by the MDPI (Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute) in Switzerland (2021), global production of tires in 2022 is estimated at 2.4 billion units per annum while tires, as mentioned above, are also being recycled and (to some extent) reused or disposed of.

Due to their non-biodegradability and bulkiness, the landfilling of scrap tires has been gradually replaced by recycling strategies. In Europe, which is responsible for 20% of new tire production (300 million car tires and 18 million truck tires per year), almost 95% of ELTs (3556 Mt) were processed in 2019, resulting in the generation of materials (55%) and energy (40%) recovery.

This is mainly due to the European Union's ELT regulations, which cover not only the collection of tires by certain entities, but also their recovery and recycling. Since the introduction of these directives, a reduction of the tire inventory and landfill capacity from 78% (1994) to 5% (2019) has been observed.

Tire re-utilization strategies also depend heavily on their condition, with used tires classified as scrap tires and partially worn tires. The recycling of scrap tires includes the following markets:

- Artificial turf (30 % – Europe in 2019, however, as of 2023 the EU is supposed to prohibit the use of artificial turf granulate)
- Sports arenas and playgrounds (20 %)
- Molded products (26 %)
- Asphalt and pavement (2 %)
- Civil engineering (3 %)

On the other hand, partially worn tires can be retreaded (i.e. tread and sidewall rubber replaced) and put back on the market, resulting in 70% of recovered material savings (thanks to material recovery and extended life) and lower CO2 emissions (24%), water consumption (19%) and air pollution from particulate matter (21%). (Tasalloti et al., 2021.)

However, this strategy is not the solution for ELT management because tires cannot be retreaded and moreover, the quality and safety of retreaded tires is definitely reduced, which is particularly noticeable when driving at high speeds. Although important steps have been taken towards ELT management, research is essential to improve the existing processes and to develop more efficient alternatives.

Pyrolysis technologies, in particular, have great potential for recycling scrap tires, as they offer both - material and energy recovery.

What Exactly is Pyrolysis?

In general terms, "pyrolysis" means the decomposition of chemical products. Accordingly, the process is a way to recover energy from industrial or domestic waste materials or to recover certain substances. Pyrolysis processes have been used by mankind for centuries, for example to produce charcoal from coal and biomass as a base material. Pyrolysis comprises the thermal decomposition of organic substances at high temperatures, usually between 400 °C and 800 °C. The main difference between pyrolysis and incineration is that it is not a process of combustion. The main difference between this process and the combustion or gasification of substances is significant: In pyrolysis, combustion takes place in the absence of oxygen. This allows the carbon compounds and the hydrocarbon compounds to be retained (Gerdes, 2001).

The Status Quo – What Happens in Conjunction with the Used Tire Pyrolysis?

Compared to other ELT management strategies, pyrolysis offers several advantages in terms of operational, economic, and environmental aspects. For example, compared to incineration, pyrolysis delivers higher energetic efficiency and lower emissions of particulate matter and air pollutants (Costa et al., 2022). The thermal treatment of ELTs is particularly interesting due to the composition, but also challenging, since, as described earlier, different types of tires (e.g., car or truck tires) can include many different components.

To reiterate the numbers: Tires are composed of natural and/or synthetic rubber (60-65%), carbon black (25-35%), chemicals and minerals added during the manufacturing process (e.g., vulcanizing agents such as sulfur and zinc oxide and additives such as silica), and textile, rope, and steel belts for strength (Costa et al., 2022).

The differences in the raw material composition pose major challenges for ELT pyrolysis as they affect the consistency of the obtained products. ELT pyrolysis research has focused on the optimization of pyrolysis reactors and operating conditions and their influence on base materials recovery, product distribution and composition.

Results of the ELT Pyrolysis – What Do We Gain?

The rubber fractions of ELTs makes it possible to manufacture three different types of pyrolysis products:

- Steel
- Synthesis gas (gas-like compositions with a low molecular weight)
- Pyrolysis oil (liquid compositions resulting from the condensation of the gas)
- Recovered Carbon Black (rCB),

Yield and composition of these products strongly depend on the base material composition, reactor type and pyrolysis operating conditions (especially temperature) (Beston Group, other documents)

Market and Manufacturers

In recent years, the pyrolysis technology market has evolved due to new processes and other innovations. Compared to other industries, it is not yet very large, but it is growing steadily - ultimately also thanks to the growing environmental awareness of the industry, but also because of the business and technical opportunities within the industry. Some notable manufacturers with interesting technological approaches are for example:

- Scandinavian Enviro Systems (Enviro)
- Bolder Industries
- Delta Energy
- Pyrum Innovations AG
- Circotec

Hence, it is safe to say that ELT management does not only have environmental potential, but also economic potential - the market is there, and it's growing. Worldwide, about 4 billion used tires are currently stored in landfills, and about 1.8 billion more are added each year - a raw material stockpile that theoretically already exists now and from which various materials can be recovered. But let's go back to the beginning: As you likely recall, we actually wanted to implement a recycling economy affiliated with tires. What does it look like? I will address this subject matter in the next chapter ...

THE REVOLUTION – VIRGIN RECOVERED CARBON BLACK?

As we were able to establish in the last chapter, general recycling processes with regard to used tires are by no means new and have even become established worldwide - although there are obviously some exceptions.

If we now evaluate the various influential factors, an economic loop that works becomes discernible, but the "creation of recycled value generation" or a "recycling economy" still is not achieved. The product lifecycle of tires, in particular, plays a decisive role here. As we now know, Carbon Black is one of the most important components of tires or rubber products. The Fraunhofer Institute (2022) explains: "It is a high-tech product with a market volume of 15 million tons, which offers economic advantages and - when considering the material alone - appears to be ecologically unproblematic. However, the production of Carbon Black and the associated high level of CO₂ emissions are becoming increasingly problematic. [...] After all, of the more than 15 million metric tons of Carbon Black produced worldwide each year, 80 percent is used in technical rubber-resin materials or tires, with an upward trend. Carbon Black is an extremely stable chemical compound as well as a structural form that is retained in a wide variety of applications. The material is thus predestined for recycling."

The Problem: The Value Chain is Not Closed

In the pyrolysis process of scrap tires, the gaseous fraction is recovered and condensed into liquid fuels - Recovered Carbon Black (RCB) is produced as a solid by-product. And although the recycling process ultimately remains "incomplete," a huge global pyrolysis market exists with more than 1,000 pyrolysis plants worldwide, though the majority of these operate at a low tech level.

The Fraunhofer Institute (2022) provides insights into this subject matter as well: "For every ton of scrap tires processed, about one-third is Carbon Black - a mixture of carbon black, ash and coke. This material could be reused for industrial applications, but so far it is not an adequate alternative for the primary resource carbon black. This is because the proportion of mineral ash is high; it usually contains zinc sulfides, zinc oxides, silicon dioxide, aluminum oxides and, for example, cobalt compounds. These inorganic substances cover the active surface of the carbon black, which is required for industrial applications. In addition, they are also of concern for health

reasons, limiting higher-value reuse. In addition, it can cause problems in technical products such as tires when the strength and durability of the rubber decreases. The substance cannot easily be used as a colorant either. The achievable black value is low, as is the degree of hardness of the mineral content."

This material cannot solve the problems of the Carbon Black industry: Instead, it must be upgraded to a true substitute for conventional Carbon Black, and the mineral residues must be extracted without significantly altering their properties.

Executive Summary:

- In an oxygen-free environment, old tires (ELTs) are thermally treated in a reactor at temperatures between 300 and 600 °C (depending on the system) for a defined period of time. Rubber turns into gas, which condenses into oil. The only remaining material besides the steel is a carbonaceous residue, also known as recovered Carbon Black, which still contains silica and zinc fractions.
- The normal output is: 33% raw Recovered Carbon Black, 45% oil, 14% steel, 8% gas.
- The raw Recovered Carbon Black, on the other hand, has a very limited marketability because it is contaminated with residues: only 80% Carbon Black remains, 20% of which is ash. The material can therefore only be used for the production of new tires to an extremely limited extent, as the required properties of the Carbon Black cannot be achieved due to the contamination of the ash.

But what if it were possible to process recovered industrial Carbon Black in such a way that the material is almost 100% pure and can thus be used for tire production? The fact is: It would then be possible to place the entire tire industry into a recycling value chain, a real recycling-based economy.

I assure you, it is possible - right now.

Revolution: Cleaning Process Deploying Nano Technology

RCB Nanotechnologies GmbH is a company I personally support as an investor and that has developed as well as tested exciting approaches to recovering Carbon Black together with the Fraunhofer Institute - this has resulted in a technology thanks to which recovered Carbon Black can actually be used as a complete substitute for virgin industrial Carbon Black.

The Prerequisites

To achieve this, mineral residues must be extracted without changing their useful properties. The particular challenge here is the extraction of ash, which can then also be used as a basis for the production of various products. To that end, the Fraunhofer Institute has developed and patented a process based on a wet-chemical, hydrothermal treatment. This approach is groundbreaking and worthwhile: Eco-guidelines can be met 100 % - without toxic waste.

This not only makes it possible to recycle scrap tires in a truly sustainable way, but also to create a recycled base material for three independent product groups:

- Industrial Carbon Black (highly pure Recovered Carbon Black)
- Products based on silicon dioxide (varnishes, paints, construction materials, etc.)
- Zinc based products (semiconductors, pharmaceuticals, etc.)

The Solution: Sustainable Recycling Methods

"That's all well and good," you may think, "but it is simply not possible to produce a tire without pure industrial Carbon Black. You're right: even if natural rubber can be obtained under the best ecologically sound conditions, it still has to be vulcanized. And conventional recovered Carbon Black that is a residue after recycling is not adequate in terms of quality.

The Process

1. Thermal processing

Given that the raw RCB comes from different pyrolysis plants and because, as a result, the quality and properties of the material vary greatly, all volatile oil residues and polymer residues of the raw RCB are first removed by a controlled thermal process - as indicated above - without strongly influencing the characteristics of the Carbon Black.

2. Nano processing

The chemical retroactive treatment of crude RCB produces up to 99% pure carbon. The ash content is reduced, as well as silica and zinc are separated and sustainably marketed as recovered products.

3. Mechanic processing

After the purification process and controlled grinding, the new "RCB 2.0@" is now available in particle sizes around <math><10 \mu\text{m}</math> and is formed into pellets tailored to the application requirements of the industry.

Linear economy

a)

b)

c)

The Result: A Closed Value Chain

What emerges from this is obvious - a true recycling economy: RCB-Nanotechnologies' refining process upgrades Recovered Carbon Black into a truly sustainable alternative to virgin Carbon Black. At the same time, valuable new silica- and zinc-based products are obtained from the process. These recovered products can also be used for the production of new tires and replace the corresponding industrially produced raw materials.

Potenzial Kreislaufwirtschaft: Einfluss auf die Umwelt

We should be aware that recycling economies are fundamentally more resource-efficient and therefore also more valuable ecologically, economically and socially - because when these three components are brought into harmony, we can speak of true sustainability.

Innovative solutions for the sustainable recycling of end-of-life tires (ELTs) in particular have enormous potential to achieve the European Union's climate targets by achieving CO2 neutrality by 2050 and a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by a minimum of 55% by 2030. Only effective and industrially proven solutions such as the process described above can help achieve these climate objectives.

And some figures can be predicted: Replacing 50% of the world's industrial carbon black with recovered carbon black would save 15 million tons of fossil resources and reduce CO2 emissions by 23 million tons per year.

Input	New Tyre (Kg CO ₂)	Retreaded Tyre (Kg CO ₂)
Materials	48.6	31.1
Transport	9.9	8.3
Energy	31.4	22.5
Waste	-0.1	-0.1
End-of-Life	-2.5	-1.1
Total Carbon Footprint	87.2	60.7

One example to support this scientifically is a 2020 study conducted by the University of Luxembourg on the implementation of a recycling economy for the disposal of used tires in a developing country (in this case Nigeria) - from which an enormous savings potential can be derived. The production of new tires has a higher carbon footprint (emissions) than remanufacturing/retreading. For example, 74%, 67% and 76% of new car, truck and off-road tires, respectively, are carbon-based materials. For retreaded tires, the figure is about 50% in each case. Of course, it must be pointed out that in developing countries, the uncontrolled burning of tires contributes to greenhouse gas emissions.

Logically, figures depicting an actual recycling economy do not (yet) exist, but the potential is enormous. As always, strategically sensible planning for implementation is an important factor.

Outlook

According to the Spanish Institute of Polymer Science and Technology (2021), sustainable mobility and recycling economy models require a long-term vision based on three main pillars: the sustainable use of resources, technological innovation and economic growth. In this context, the primary tire manufacturing sectors should expand the use of renewable material resources, develop innovative solutions - such as the one described above - and invest in breakthrough technologies to incorporate more recycled and renewable materials into their tires and extend their useful life. Examples of such applications exist already and form the core of the strategic plans envisioned by the leading tire manufacturers. The Bridgestone Group has set a goal of using 100% sustainable materials in its products by 2050 and beyond; while Michelin is investing in high-tech recycling so that tires are 100% recycled by 2045. Similarly, all these measures should generate new business models and lead to sustainable economic growth. The challenge is to ensure that any process that achieves its technical goals is also economically viable and therefore has good commercial potential. However, industries should not work for themselves alone.

CONCLUSIONS

As you now know, the dream of the availability of real green tires is truly worthwhile. The groundbreaking technology explained in the last chapter shows that this is no longer part of utopian beliefs but actually has potential of becoming reality the world over. New tires can be produced again from old tires; 100% of all components of the used tire can be sensibly processed and reintegrated at the start of the production process of new tires. The fact that ingenious technical inventions are bringing us closer to the goal of actually living in harmony with nature becomes clear once again. All major resource-consuming areas of daily life must be developed into circular economies. No longer may we regard products as "waste" at the end of their useful life, but as raw materials from which we can develop something else. For it is not only the information in this paper that makes it clear what a major impact this can have on the environment, this must be evident to all.

It is important to understand that we are not "on the verge" of a climate disaster: it has in fact already begun. We cannot wait for something to change on its own. For this reason it is now more urgent than ever to invest more into technologies and their applications. For this to happen, politicians will have to rethink their strategies. The simple creation of the technological framework for a green value chain within the tire industry was only possible because one company spent several years engaging in privately funded research - and it has achieved the breakthrough!

I have personally provided significant funding for this research at my own risk and without any certainty that it would be successful. A change in thinking must take place and every person who is able to should help. Without sustainable entrepreneurship, a high level of commitment, and reasonable risk-taking, a vision can never become reality. Many more funding sources for environmental technologies need to be created and made more easily accessible for start-ups. From my own experience, I can say that funding often does not reach small companies - too often I have personally tried to get support from government agencies and other funding sources to no avail. Anything that is to be created in the interest of a long-term environmental and climate focus must be supported without red tape. In my opinion, Germany, has already missed the boat on the digital economy and unfortunately does not play a role in this area on a global scale.

Nevertheless, we still enjoy worldwide recognition for being one of the leading nations in the field of engineering, and quite rightfully so. Germany has made a decisive contribution to the

energy turnaround to date. Yet we must not rest on our laurels. We have already had to watch our entire - formerly world-leading - solar industry slip out of competitiveness. We no longer play a role in the manufacture of solar panels. However, politicians now have a unique opportunity to once again allocate a large budget towards sustainable innovations and groundbreaking inventions in the interest of a positive future: Germany has the potential to become the leading nation in the development of several new environmental technologies. I am convinced of this - our politicians should be equally as convinced!

U-turns must be made in the most diverse of fields: For example, the pricing of products needs to be defined differently. A product should be priced according to the costs of its production, consumption, and disposal. The current pricing of products and the resulting perception is simply wrong: A car is generally considered to be a role model in terms of having a small environmental footprint if it is highly economical in terms of (energy) consumption. But this one-sided communication is not only based on erroneous beliefs, it is also inaccurate. On the one hand, a car's consumption depends on the way it is driven - deviations of well over 50% can easily occur in different scenarios. On the other hand, consumption is only one sub-component of the vehicle's overall environmental balance. The aspects of production and disposal are just as important. There are huge differences here, and in some cases certain products are promoted absurdly for precisely this reason of cost concealment.

Other examples include all products that can only be manufactured in Asia as a result of globalization and the ever-increasing pressure on prices. Here, too, prices need to be reconsidered: We currently calculate for a commodity - e.g. a sneaker - only the estimated costs from the factory in Asia plus the import or export costs. thus assuming that the sneaker can be produced "so cheaply" only in Asia. This is fundamentally wrong, however, because in due course we will all collectively pay the true environmental price for it!

If we were to forthrightly compute the price and take all factors into account, the sneaker from Asia would probably even be more expensive than if it were made in Europe - where it is ultimately sold. How much more expensive would the shoe be if the same strict environmental regulations applied to production facilities in Asia as are being implemented in Europe and the United States? How expensive would the shoe be if not only the transportation costs were factored into

the equation, but also the environmental impact of global land and sea transport (presented based on the actual figures)?

As previously mentioned, the perspective on things must change and the focus must be increasingly placed on technologies that help us shape a positive future. Each effective initiative deserves attention and support. Politicians must ensure that significantly better environmental technologies are always promoted (after sufficiently long tests), so that they can nevertheless quickly become established and hold their own against old established technologies, which often have too strong a lobby. Above all, state institutions must urgently place the environmental focus in the foreground of all procurement procedures.

Our example of the green tire shows what a big impact innovative technologies can potentially have on the carbon footprint of products. The point is to promote disruptive technologies on a grand scale and then accelerate their scaling through all possible measures. We are all recklessly building up "environmental debt" on the shoulders of future generations - this is in my view selfish and wrong. We have the means to change things - yet we are too lethargic to take the necessary steps to do so. We humans do not own the earth, we are guests - and can be expelled. Our self-image of being the owners of the earth goes so far that we burden, pollute or even destroy it without any inhibition. The consequences will not be long in coming - in fact they are already clearly in evidence. This must stop! There is no plan and most importantly, there is no alternative, no planet B. We have the chance to lead an environmentally friendly and sustainable life on earth without overburdening future generations with endless environmental mortgages. Everyone should start in their own backyards. It is not too late

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Jan Malkus studied theoretical computer science at the Technical University of Braunschweig, Germany, and specialised in corporate management. He now runs his own family office and invested successfully as a serial entrepreneur in a number of companies. His heart beats for the environment, so he got involved in many promising environmental technologies at an early stage. In addition to environmental technologies, he primarily invests in the FinTech sector and wants to set new standards - also through state-of-the-art technology (such as blockchain paired with artificial intelligence).

For more information about the author, visit www.janmalkus.com

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